

The Role of Social Media, Altruistic and Egoistic Motivations, Subjective Norms, And EWOM In Shaping Green Cosmetics Consumption Behavior: A Case Study of Generation Z in Ho Chi Minh City

Man Minh CAO

International University - Vietnam National University Hcmc; Quarter 33, Linh Xuan Ward, Hcmc, Vietnam

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 12 August 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Man Minh CAO</p>	<p>This study explores the relationship between Social Media, Altruistic and Egoistic Motivations, Subjective Norms and Electronic Word-Of-Mouth (EWOM) in shaping the green cosmetics buying behavior of Generation Z in Ho Chi Minh City in Vietnam. A quantitative approach was adopted in this research whereby primary data was obtained from 302 respondents from Generation Z. The findings reveal that Social Media significantly impacts both altruistic (environmental) and egoistic (health) motivations, along with Subjective Norms, which in turn drive purchase intention and behavior. Also, EWOM plays an important role in consumers' choices by providing additional information through experiences and opinions that have been shared. This information provides marketers and policy makers with practical suggestions on how to develop appropriate digital communication strategies designed for the youth, who are environmentally friendly and IT-savvy to promote green consumption.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Social Media, Altruistic Motivation, Egoistic Motivation, Subjective Norms, Electronic Word-Of-Mouth (EWOM), Green Cosmetics.</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing public concern over hazardous chemicals in cosmetics, along with rising ethical issues in the industry, has driven the growth of the organic cosmetics market (Franca & Ueno, 2020). Young consumers can influence and disseminate awareness about the product by creating referrals on both virtual and actual media, especially generation Z, known for its active engagement with social media and distinct value (Dolot, 2018). In addition, according to (Le et al, 2022), young people's inclination to purchase environmentally friendly goods and their willingness to spend more on ethical products is greatly impacted by their interpersonal dynamics with family and friends and their environmental cognizance. Social media platforms have become a modern means of communication where consumers communicate their purchasing behavior, experiences, likes and preferences for particular brands (Emini & Zequiri, 2021).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Definition of Key Concept

2.1.1 Definition of Green Cosmetics

Due to growing consumer interest in natural, vegan and organic products ranging from food to cosmetics,

sustainable beauty has become more and more popular in recent years (Hirata et al., 2022). Furthermore, natural or organic raw materials can be used to make cosmetics without the use of industrialized inputs (Hirata et al., 2022). Products made from plants, minerals or animals are known as "green cosmetics" (Limbu & Ahamed, 2023).

2.1.2 Generation Z (Gen Z)

Generation Z regards social media as a fundamental component of their daily existence (Mude & Undale, 2023). They are accustomed to consuming information rapidly, processing it efficiently, and incorporating the results of the digital revolution into their daily lives with ease (Cismariu & Hosu, 2019). They are not only highly active on social media but also cognizant of sustainable lifestyles and their responsibilities toward the environment. Despite their youth, they aim to obtain and utilize eco-friendly products (Noor et al., 2017).

2.1.3 The role of Social Media

The new generation uses social media before purchasing products to learn more about their attributes (Xie & Madni, 2023). Social media environmental practices can act as a template to raise public awareness of environmental preservation (Sun & Xing, 2022). Individuals influenced by

social media marketing are readily swayed by social norms within sustainable consumption groups (Sun & Wang, 2020).

2.1.4 EWOM and Green Cosmetics Purchase Behavior

Aslam et al (2011) stated that firsthand experience of others may be highly useful because it had some truth and was easily trusted. They believed that close relatives, friends, family and acquaintances always provided an honest view that was entirely trustworthy and made the selection easier. EWOM is the term for unofficial, non-commercial online conversation between two or more customers regarding brands, goods or services (Albarq & Al Doghan, 2020). EWOM would disseminate far more data to shoppers, thus influencing purchase behavior (Kumar & Pandey, 2023).

2.1.5 Altruistic Motivation and Green Cosmetics Purchase Intention

According to the study of Alam et al. (2023), human motivated by altruism is considered unselfish and environmentally conscious, prioritizing the wellbeing of others in the preservation of the natural ecosystem. Liao et al., (2019) posits that environmental concern significantly impacts behavioral intention, which subsequently mediates sustainable consumer behavior. Moreover, the research of (Arisal & Atalar, 2016) shows how environmental concern or altruistic motivation can directly impact the green products purchase intention, the outcome is supported by (Maichum et al., 2017) and (Zhu et al., 2020).

2.1.6 Egoistic Motivation and Green Cosmetics Purchase Intention

According to the study of (Jin et al., 2017), more and more consumers are incorporating health-related values into their purchasing decisions. Indeed, when purchasing food products, consumers prioritize health and are concerned about food-related issues (Sinh, 2024). However, not only having attention on organic food, consumer environmental friendly products also have a significant impact on their well-being and health (Zinoubi, 2020), this result is similar with the study of (Alam et al., 2023) about the impact of egoistic motivation (concern for health) on the green products purchase intention.

2.1.7 Subjective Norms and Green Cosmetics Purchase Intention

Noor et al (2020) states that subjective norms are crucial aspect that influence customer purchasing decisions for specific products. In the realm of online commerce, subjective norms significantly affect clients' purchase intentions (Savita & Verma, 2017). In the green products field, if customers believe that their choice aligns with the standards that their friends and family know and value, they could be more inclined to buy (Lius & Salim, 2024). Moreover, not just family and friends, but also influencer and celebrity posts, topic groups, and reviews can all be effective ways to increase awareness of and desire to buy green products (Kumar & Pandey, 2023).

2.1.8 Green Cosmetics Purchase Intention and Green Cosmetics Purchase Behavior

According to the study of Brown et al. (2003), actual purchasing rates are greater for clients who intend to purchase certain goods than for those who have no intention of purchasing. Thus, green purchase intention serves as a significant predictor of green purchase behavior, indicating that a consumer's intention to purchase positively and directly affects their actual purchasing behavior (Naz et al., 2020). The findings align with the study by Kumar and Pandey (2023), which indicated that intention influences purchasing habits, thereby demonstrating that Green Purchase Intention positively affects Green Purchase Behavior.

2.2 Prior Research

Kumar and Pandey (2023) assert that firms cannot thrive without the backing of social media. In this study, Kumar and Pandey want to understand the influence of social media on motivation, egotism, and altruism, as well as the resulting effect on the inclination to make ecologically sustainable purchases. The study incorporates the construct EWOM to evaluate the influence of subjective norms on the desire to purchase environmentally friendly products and subsequently, the effect of this intention on green purchasing behavior.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of Kumar & Panday (2023)

However, in Vietnam, there is no research examining the influence of altruistic motivation and egoistic motivation on consumer behavior on the purchase of green cosmetics, especially within the framework of social media. Consequently, utilizing the framework established by Kumar and Pandey (2023), an additional framework has been

developed to examine not only a specific category of green products, namely green cosmetics, but also to elucidate how these factors influence the purchasing intentions and actual behaviors of generation Z in Ho Chi Minh city, Vietnam, regarding green cosmetics.

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

Proposed Hypotheses

- H1: Social media positively affects customers' Altruistic Motivation for green cosmetics.
- H2: Social Media positively affects customers' Egoistic Motivation for green cosmetics.
- H3: Social Media positively affects customers' Subjective norms for green cosmetics.

- H4: EWOM positively affects consumers' Green Cosmetics Purchasing Behavior
- H5: Customers' intention to buy green cosmetics is positively impacted by Altruistic Motivation (concern for environment).
- H6: Customers' intention to buy green cosmetics is positively impacted by Egoistic Motivation (concern for health).

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H7: Customers’ intention to buy green cosmetics is positively impacted by Subjective Norms.

H8: Purchase behavior for green cosmetics is positively impacted by Green Cosmetics Purchase Intention.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Sampling and sample size

3.1.1 Sample Size

Generation Z's purchasing behavior regarding eco-friendly cosmetics in Ho Chi Minh City is the focus of this study, which seeks to examine the interplay between social media, motivations, and subjective norms. Hair et al. (2014) suggests a sample size ten times greater than the entire number of indicators used. There are a total of twenty-two questions on this research measurement scale. Therefore, 220 respondents would be the ideal number for the sample.

3.1.2 Target respondents

In the study of (Kumar & Pandey, 2023), the researchers only target individuals over 18 years old. Combining with the research of (Alam et al., 2023), the criteria for respondents has been given, specifically targeting individuals over 18 years old and having past shopping experience on green cosmetics via social media. Furthermore, the age range is limited because the research focus is on generation Z.

3.2 Questionnaire Design and Measurement items

3.2.2 Measurement items

Part I: Green cosmetics purchase behavior of generation Z

The assessment utilized a five-point Likert Scale, spanning from 1 to 5, with 1 indicating “strongly disagree”, 2 representing “disagree”, 3 denoting “neutral”, 4 signifying “agree”, and 5 corresponding to “strongly agree”.

Table 1: Scales of Variables

Measuring Items for Variable	Sources	Scale	
Green Cosmetics Purchase Intention (GI)			
GI1	Chin et al. (2018) & Jaini et al (2020)	5-point Likert Scale	
			Cosmetics that are less harmful to the environment will be my only choice going forward.
GI2			I would transfer my loyalty to eco-friendly cosmetics for environmental considerations.
GI3	I am considering rising my investment in green cosmetics		
Green Cosmetics Purchase Behavior (GB)			
GB1	Jain et al. (2020)	5-point Likert Scale	
			I only purchase environmentally friendly cosmetics that I often use
GB2			An essential part of my daily practice is using green cosmetics
GB3	In recent months, I have been buying eco-friendly cosmetics		
Electronic Word of Mouth (EWOM)			
EWOM1	Jain et al. (2020)	5-point Likert Scale	
			I frequently use social media to share my opinions about eco-friendly cosmetics
EWOM2			EWOM on social media platforms influences consumers’ decisions to buy eco-friendly cosmetics
EWOM3	Facebook has been my primary means of self-expression		

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	Subjective Norms (SN)		
SN1	The inclusion of sustainable materials in cosmetics products is recommended by experts	Chin et al. (2018)	5-point Likert Scale
SN2	Those who matter most in my life force me to use eco-friendly cosmetics		
SN3	I am encouraged to use eco-friendly cosmetics by my family and close friends		
	Social media (SM)		
SM1	My green cosmetics purchases are influenced by Social Media	Gunawan and Huarng (2015) & Goldsmith et al. (2000)	5-point Likert Scale
SM2	Social media is my primary source for green cosmetics updates		
SM3	Social media is a trustworthy platform for green cosmetics reviews		
	Altruistic Motivation (AL)		
AL1	Because the products are manufactured in an eco-friendly way, I find it ethically appealing to purchase this line of green cosmetics	Sánchez-Ferández et al. (2009), Roberts and Bacon (1997), & Izagirre-Olaizola et al. (2015)	5-point Likert Scale
AL2	The sustainable preservation of this eco-friendly cosmetics brand aligns with my moral principles		
AL3	To live, individuals must cultivate a positive relationship with nature.		
AL4	When I go shopping for cosmetics, I give preference to eco-friendly products		
	Egoistic Motivation (EG)		
EG1	I prioritize health when shopping for green cosmetics	Tarkiainen and Sundquist (2005) & Sony and Ferguson (2015)	5-point Likert Scale
EG2	I carefully choose green items in order to maintain my fitness		
EG3	I still think about the health benefits of green cosmetics when making a decision		

Part II: Demographic Information

The questionnaires include the respondents' demographic information, such as gender, age, and employment status.

Table 2: Scale of Demographic Information

Value	Code	Items	Measurement Scales
Gender	Gender	What is your gender?	1 = “Male” 2 = “Female” 3 = “Prefer not to say”
Age	Age	How old are you?	1 = “18-20” 2 = “21-23” 3 = “24-26” 4 = “27-29”
Employment Status	Employment Status	What best describes your employment status?	1 = “Undergraduate Student” 2 = “Employed” 3 = “Freelancer” 4 = “Other”

3.3 Data Collection and Analysis

3.3.1 Data Collection Procedure

Questionnaires were distributed to target respondents using a multifaceted approach that included both online and offline methods. The primary dissemination mechanism was Google Forms. Furthermore, offline approaches included distributing paper surveys to young people in Ho Chi Minh City. In addition to online and offline methods, numerous internet channels were used to increase visibility and accessibility. Social media sites like Facebook and Zalo were used to reach a larger audience.

The questionnaire distribution lasted for a month, from November 2024 to December 2024. A total of 302 eligible respondents were selected using convenience and non-probability convenient sampling approaches in Ho Chi Minh City in Vietnam.

3.3.2 Data Analysis Method

A basic statistical analysis of the sample will be performed utilizing SPSS 20. This tool will facilitate the calculation of Cronbach's Alpha for each variable. Smart-PLS 3.0 is later utilized to perform a more thorough examination of the data.

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques

3.4.1 Measurement Model

3.4.1.1 Internal consistency reliability

Cronbach’s Alpha scores of 0.7 or higher are generally regarded as satisfactory (Hair et al., 2010). It assesses the degree to which a collection of elements represents the core concept or latent variable. A higher

composite dependability signifies a more accurate depiction of the construct (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

3.4.1.2 Variance Inflation Factor

A VIF greater than 5 is considered indicative of significant multicollinearity and necessitates scrutiny (Hair et al., 2010).

3.4.1.3 Validity (Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity)

Higher AVEs suggest enhanced convergent validity (Bahkia et al., 2021). Fornell & Larcker (1981) established that an Average Variance Extracted (AVE) criterion of 0.5 or higher signifies robust convergent validity, indicating that the construct accounts for more than half of the variance in its indicators.

Mohammadi and Mahmoodi (2019) assert that the correlation between a construct and any other construct must be less than the square root of the AVE for that construct. Meeting this criterion indicates that the construct is distinct from others and possesses adequate discriminant validity (Santos & Cirillo, 2021). If the correlation between two items exceeds the square root of their respective AVEs, it indicates potential discriminant validity issues, suggesting that the constructs may not be distinct and could measure similar concepts (Lim, 2024).

3.4.2 Structural model

3.4.2.1 Outer loadings

A commonly accepted guideline suggests that outer loadings should exceed 0.70, although no universal threshold is established. This threshold guarantees that the latent variable accounts for a minimum of 50% of the variance in the manifest variable. Lower thresholds, such as 0.40, may be

deemed acceptable in specific instances, particularly in exploratory research or when other quality criteria are satisfied (Wong, 2013).

3.4.2.2 Structural Path Significance Test

Nahm (2017) indicates that the incompatibility of data with a specific statistical model is reflected by the P value. A greater statistical incompatibility of the data with the null hypothesis is associated with a lower P value. A p-value below the significance threshold, generally established at 0.05, signifies a statistically significant relationship (Alqahtani et al., 2024).

Metrics like explained variance (R square), effect size (f^2), predictive relevance (Q square), and the quantity and importance of path coefficients are utilized to evaluate the linkages within the structural model post-assessment (Sharma et al., 2019).

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

4.1.1 Frequency

The gender distribution indicates that 164 respondents (54.3%) identify as female, whereas 138 respondents (45.7%) identify as male.

The largest group comprises individuals aged 18-20, representing 41.7% of the total respondents (126 individuals). The 21-23 age group follows closely, accounting for 35.1% (106 individuals). Respondents aged 24-26 make up 11.3% (34 individuals), while those aged 27-29 constitute 11.9% (36 individuals). These figures suggest that the majority of respondents are young adults, with a significant portion falling into the traditional college-going age range.

In terms of employment status, the majority of respondents, 184 individuals (60.9%), are undergraduate students. Employed individuals account for 26.2% (79 respondents), while freelancers make up 12.9% (39 respondents).

4.1.2 Descriptive Statistic

4.1.2.1 Green Cosmetics Purchase Intention (GI)

Customers have varied assessments of their Green Cosmetics Purchase Intention (GI). The overall mean scores for the three items (GI1, GI2, GI3) show a moderately low intention to purchase green cosmetics, with mean scores ranging from 2.77 to 2.88.

4.1.2.2 Green Cosmetics Purchase Behavior (GB)

The data reflects a relatively low overall behavior towards purchasing green cosmetics. The mean scores for the three items (GB1, GB2, GB3) range from 2.87 to 2.90, suggesting that, on average, consumers are not highly engaged in purchasing green cosmetics.

4.1.2.3 Electronic Word of Mouth (EWOM)

The Electronic Word-of-Mouth (EWOM) elucidates customers' perspectives regarding the influence of online evaluations and suggestions on their attitudes towards eco-friendly cosmetics. The average scores for the three questions (EWOM1, EWOM2, EWOM3) span from 2.85 to 2.89, indicating that consumers exhibit a neutral to modestly favorable disposition regarding the impact of EWOM on their purchasing behavior.

4.1.2.4 Subjective Norms (SN)

The Subjective Norms (SN) data indicates the impact of social pressure and the views of others on customers' attitudes toward green cosmetics. The average scores for the three questions (SN1, SN2, SN3) span from 2.77 to 3.01, suggesting a moderate impact of Subjective Norms on consumers' decision-making processes.

4.1.2.5 Social Media (SM)

The Social Media (SM) data reveals the role of Social Media platforms in shaping consumers' attitudes and behaviors towards green cosmetics. The mean scores for the three items (SM1, SM2, SM3) range from 3.35 to 3.42, indicating a moderate level of influence of Social Media on consumers' perceptions and intentions.

4.1.2.6 Altruistic Motivation (AL)

The Altruistic Motivation (AL) data reflects consumers' motivations to purchase green cosmetics based on a desire to benefit the environment or society. The mean scores for the four items (AL1, AL2, AL3, AL4) range from 2.78 to 2.99, indicating a moderate level of altruistic motivation among consumers.

4.1.2.7 Egoistic Motivation (EG)

The Egoistic Motivation data reflects consumers' motivations to purchase green cosmetics based on personal benefits, such as health. The mean scores for the three items (EG1, EG2, EG3) range from 2.91 to 3.01, indicating a moderate level of Egoistic Motivation.

4.2 Reliability Analysis

Table 3: Variable Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite Reliability

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Conclusion
AL	0.849	0.898	Acceptable
EG	0.805	0.885	Acceptable
EWOM	0.829	0.897	Acceptable
GB	0.781	0.871	Acceptable
GI	0.801	0.883	Acceptable
SM	0.878	0.922	Acceptable
SN	0.854	0.911	Acceptable

Table 12 demonstrates that all variables (AL, EG, EWOM, GB, GI, SM, and SN) possess Cronbach’s Alpha values surpassing 0.7, signifying that the items within each scale are strongly correlated and facilitate a reliable assessment.

All variables in Table 12 exhibit Composite dependability ratings exceeding 0.7, indicating the reliability of the measurement scales.

4.3 Measurement Model Assessment

4.3.1 Outer Loadings

According to the Table 20, all constructs meet or surpass the usual criteria of 0.7 for outer loadings, indicating that the indicators are valid measurements of their latent constructions.

Table 4: Outer loadings

	AL	EG	EWOM	GB	GI	SM	SN
AL1	0.832						
AL2	0.831						
AL3	0.852						
AL4	0.801						
EG1		0.853					
EG2		0.858					
EG3		0.834					
EWOM1			0.850				
EWOM2			0.843				
EWOM3			0.895				
GB1				0.796			
GB2				0.838			
GB3				0.862			
GI1					0.839		
GI2					0.853		
GI3					0.845		
SM1						0.864	
SM2						0.893	
SM3						0.923	
SN1							0.880
SN2							0.865
SN3							0.895

4.4 Validity Analysis

4.4.1 Convergent Validity Test

In this case, none of the variables were removed because their AVEs exceeded 0.5.

Table 5: Variable Average Variance Extracted

Variables	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Result
AL	0.688	Acceptable
EG	0.719	Acceptable
EWOM	0.745	Acceptable
GB	0.693	Acceptable
GI	0.715	Acceptable
SM	0.799	Acceptable
SN	0.774	Acceptable

4.4.2 Discriminant Validity

The Fornell-Larcker Criterion Test indicated that all latent variables demonstrated discriminant validity, as each square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) met the necessary threshold.

Table 6: Fornell-Larcker Criterion Analysis

	AL	EG	EWOM	GB	GI	SM	SN
AL	0.829						
EG	0.715	0.848					
EWOM	0.105	0.049	0.863				
GB	0.689	0.521	0.187	0.833			
GI	0.669	0.785	-0.150	0.411	0.846		
SM	0.284	0.335	0.031	0.341	0.283	0.894	
SN	0.659	0.717	-0.007	0.536	0.746	0.243	0.880

4.5 Hypothesis Testing

4.5.1 Collinearity assessment

Table 23 indicates that all structures possess VIF values below 5, signifying that the structural model is devoid of collinearity.

Table 7: Collinearity assessment

	VIF
AL1	1.990
AL2	1.872
AL3	2.016
AL4	1.760
EG1	1.829
EG2	1.732
EG3	1.679
EWOM1	2.087
EWOM2	1.656
EWOM3	2.506
GB1	1.599
GB2	1.702
GB3	1.583
GI1	1.689
GI2	1.737
GI3	1.721
SM1	2.672

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SM2	2.077
SM3	2.790
SN1	2.208
SN2	1.906
SN3	2.386

4.5.2 Coefficient of determination (R²)

Green cosmetics purchase intention (GI) serves as a critical mediator between motivations and actual purchase behavior. With a strong R² of 0.691, the predictors in this model explain nearly 70% of the variance in intention,

demonstrating that motivations (both altruistic and egoistic), subjective norms, and potentially other factors significantly influence intention. The R² value of green cosmetics purchase behavior (GB) is 0.232, suggesting that intention explains about 23.2% of the variance in behavior.

Table 8: R-Squared values

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
AL	0.081	0.078
EG	0.112	0.109
GB	0.232	0.227
GI	0.691	0.688
SN	0.059	0.056

Figure 3: R Square values

4.5.3 Predictive Relevance (Q²)

Table 25's positive Q square value indicates that the model performs well in terms of prediction, confirming the

soundness of the variable formulation and its applicability in capturing variation in the observed data.

Table 9: Q Square values

	SSO	SSE	Q² (=1-SSE/SSO)
AL1	302.000	292.912	0.030
AL2	302.000	280.850	0.070
AL3	302.000	287.298	0.049

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AL4	302.000	281.906	0.067
EG1	302.000	274.817	0.090
EG2	302.000	273.464	0.094
EG3	302.000	286.511	0.051
GB1	302.000	270.046	0.106
GB2	302.000	258.842	0.143
GB3	302.000	238.839	0.209
GI1	302.000	155.282	0.486
GI2	302.000	150.795	0.501
GI3	302.000	157.090	0.480
SN1	302.000	292.153	0.033
SN2	302.000	284.713	0.057
SN3	302.000	289.939	0.040

4.5.4 Effect size (f²)

Table 26 presents the effect sizes for all latent variables, while Table 27 illustrates the specific levels of influence. Social media exerts a negligible influence on altruistic motivation, egoistic motivation, and subjective norms. Egoistic motivation and subjective norms exert a

moderate influence on the intention to purchase green cosmetics, but altruistic motivation has a negligible effect. Moreover, the intention to purchase green cosmetics exerts a moderate influence on actual buying behavior, but electronic word-of-mouth (EWOM) has a negligible effect.

Table 10: Effect size (f²)

	AL	EG	EWOM	GB	GI	SM	SN
AL					0.021		
EG					0.255		
EWOM				0.082			
GB					0.256		
GI							
SM	0.088	0.127					0.063
SN					0.167		

Figure 4: f Square values

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Table 11: Effect size assessment

Relationship	f ²	Level of effect
AL → GI	0.021	Small
EG → GI	0.255	Medium
EWOM → GB	0.082	Small
GI → GB	0.256	Medium
SM → AL	0.088	Small
SM → EG	0.127	Small
SM → SN	0.063	Small
SN → GI	0.167	Medium

4.5.5 Size and significance of path coefficients

Table 12: Significant testing and Path coefficients (Direct Effects)

Relationships	Path Coefficients (β)	t-value	p-value	Significance (p < 0.05)
AL → GI	0.119	2.758	0.006	Yes
EG → GI	0.454	8.405	0.000	Yes
EWOM → GB	0.254	5.458	0.000	Yes
GI → GB	0.449	10.918	0.000	Yes
SM → AL	0.284	6.048	0.000	Yes
SM → EG	0.335	6.726	0.000	Yes
SM → SN	0.243	5.180	0.000	Yes
SN → GI	0.341	6.465	0.000	Yes

By using a sample size of 1,000 and bootstrapping methods, the results in table 28 shows statistical significance for all hypotheses, indicating that all 8 suggested direct relationships were statistically significant.

AL and GI have a path coefficient of 0.119, which represents their link. This reveals a weak positive association, implying that altruistic motivations may influence green cosmetics buying intentions, although their impact is limited. EG to GI have a path coefficient of 0.454, which implies that egoistic motivation has a major impact on green purchase intentions, emphasizing the role of personal rewards in shaping consumer intentions.

The path from EWOM to GB has a moderate coefficient of 0.254. This suggests that electronic word-of-mouth has an important role in influencing green cosmetics purchase behavior, although not as much as other aspects. A stronger association exists between GI and GB, with a path coefficient of 0.449. This high positive influence emphasizes

the importance of intentions in motivating real behavior, demonstrating that clear intentions frequently translate into practical consequences.

Social media (SM) emerges as a key element in the model, influencing numerous dimensions. The path from SM to AL has a moderate value of 0.284, indicating that social media plays an important influence in creating altruistic motivations. Similarly, the path from SM to EG, with a coefficient of 0.335, shows that social media has a beneficial influence on egoistic motivations. Furthermore, a path coefficient of 0.243 indicates that the association between SM and SN is weaker but still favorable.

Finally, the path from SN to GI has a coefficient of 0.341, indicating a moderate positive association. This shows that subjective norms are crucial in influencing green cosmetics purchasing intention since social expectations and norms influence people's decision-making processes.

4.5.6 Mediating relationships (indirect effects) between independent variables and green cosmetics purchase behavior

Table 13: Significant testing and path coefficients (Indirect Effects)

Relationships	Path coefficients	T value	P Values	Significance (p < 0.05)
AL → GI → GB	0.054	2.423	0.016	Yes
SM → AL → GI → GB	0.015	2.108	0.035	Yes
EG → GI → GB	0.204	6.693	0.000	Yes
SM → EG → GI → GB	0.068	4.074	0.000	Yes

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SN → GI → GB	0.153	5.719	0.000	Yes
SM → SN → GI → GB	0.037	3.486	0.001	Yes
SM → AL → GI	0.034	2.326	0.020	Yes
SM → EG → GI	0.152	4.715	0.000	Yes
SM → SN → GI	0.083	3.844	0.000	Yes

Social media (SM) significantly influences green cosmetics purchasing behavior (GB) through three indirect pathways. Social media (SM) exerts a minor influence ($\beta = 0.015, p < 0.05$) on altruistic motivation (AL), resulting in heightened buying intention (GI) and subsequent action. Furthermore, it markedly enhances egoistic motivation (EG), leading to more robust objectives and behaviors ($\beta = 0.068, p < 0.05$). SM endorses subjective norms (SN), emphasizing the significance of societal norms in influencing long-term purchase decisions ($\beta = 0.037, p < 0.05$)

Additionally, altruistic motivation ($\beta = 0.054, p < 0.05$), egoistic motivation ($\beta = 0.204, p < 0.05$), and subjective norms ($\beta = 0.153, p < 0.05$) exhibit positive and indirect influences on the purchasing behavior of green cosmetics.

Green purchase intention (GI) is an important mediatory notion. It converts altruistic and egoistic impulses, as well as external pressures such as subjective norms and social Mmedia, into actual purchasing behavior.

4.5.7 Total significant effects

Table 14: Total significant effects

Relationships	Significant direct effects	Significant indirect effects	Total effects
AL → GB	-	0.054	0.054
AL → GI	0.119	-	0.119
EG → GB	-	0.204	0.204
EG → GI	0.454	-	0.454
EWOM → GB	0.254	-	0.254
GI → GB	0.449	-	0.449
SM → AL	0.284	-	0.284
SM → EG	0.335	-	0.335
SM → GB	-	0.121	0.121
SM → GI	-	0.269	0.269
SM → SN	0.243	-	0.243
SN → GB	-	0.153	0.153
SN → GI	0.341	-	0.341

Table 30 indicates that green purchase intentions (GI) and electronic word-of-mouth (EWOM) exert the most significant direct influences on green behavior ($\beta = 0.454$ and $\beta = 0.254$, respectively). Besides direct effects, many variables, like altruistic motivation (AL) and egoistic motivation (EG), influence GB directly via green cosmetics buying intentions. Specifically, AL exhibits a minor indirect effect ($\beta = 0.054$), whereas EG reveals a considerably greater indirect influence ($\beta = 0.204$), suggesting that personal benefits are more pivotal than ethical considerations in influencing consumer intentions.

Green purchase intentions are driven by both direct and indirect effects. Among these, subjective norms (SN)

exhibit the strongest direct effect ($\beta = 0.341$), highlighting the importance of societal expectations and peer influence in driving sustainable behavior. Meanwhile, social media (SM) indirectly affects GI ($\beta = 0.269$), emphasizing its role as a facilitator that shapes consumer attitudes rather than acting as a direct influencer.

The mediator, green purchase intentions (GI), plays a pivotal role in linking indirect influences on green purchase behavior. Variables like AL and EG do not directly affect GB but contribute significantly through GI.

Social media impacts multiple variables, including altruistic motivation (AL) ($\beta = 0.284$), egoistic motivation (EG) ($\beta = 0.335$), and subjective norms (SN) ($\beta = 0.243$),

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making it a central platform for shaping motivations and societal influences. Although it does not directly affect GB,

its total indirect effect ($\beta = 0.121$) demonstrates its crucial role as a facilitator for driving green cosmetics consumerism.

Figure 5: Results of Structural Equation Modeling

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Altruistic Motivation, Egoistic Motivation and Subjective Norms effect on Green Cosmetics Purchase Intention and Green Cosmetics Purchase Behavior

Previous research (Sapri et al., 2023) and (Alam et al., 2023) support the association between altruistic motivation ($\beta = 0.119$, $p < 0.05$) and intention to purchase green cosmetics. The study of (Alam et al., 2023) demonstrates that Saudi citizens are becoming more altruistic, as seen by their willingness to address environmental issues through green purchasing intents. In addition, young customers, particularly in emerging economies like Malaysia, are more concerned with the ethical and environmental implications of their choices. According to (Sapri et al., 2023), altruistic beliefs and societal norms have a strong influence on this demographic. This shows that ethical impulses not only influence individual decisions, but also resonate with broader society trends, hence increasing demand for green cosmetics. In this study, the beta value ($\beta = 0.119$) indicates a positive but modest strength of the relationship between AL and GI, which shows that individuals with altruistic motivations are more inclined to intend to purchase eco-friendly cosmetics. Despite the modest effect size, hypothesis (H5) indicates that customers' intentions to purchase eco-friendly cosmetics are positively influenced by altruistic motive, which remains supported. Consequently, altruistic motivation influences the

purchasing intentions for green cosmetics among Generation Z in Ho Chi Minh City.

The Indian market is witnessing a growing trend towards healthier lifestyles, resulting in increased consumer interest in natural products, particularly green cosmetics (Kapoor et al., 2019). This study provides evidence of a positive correlation between egoistic motivation and the intention to purchase green cosmetics ($\beta = 0.454$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that an increase in egoistic motivation is associated with an increase in the intention to purchase green cosmetics. Furthermore, it demonstrates a moderate influence, indicating that egoistic motivation is a significant predictor of purchase intentions for green cosmetics.

Kumar and Pandey (2023) assert that both altruistic and egoistic motives significantly influence youth green purchase intentions. The egoistic benefit significantly influences green products. This study similarly demonstrates that, within the realm of green cosmetic products, egoistic motivation exerts a more significant influence than altruistic motivation on the purchase intentions of generation Z in Ho Chi Minh City. As a result, it can be seen that while altruistic concerns (environment concerns) matter, they play a less critical role in driving purchase intentions compared to egoistic motivation (health concerns).

The outcomes of this study support the influence of subjective norms (SN) on the intention to purchase green cosmetics, indicating a positive link ($\beta = 0.341$). The findings

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indicate that social pressure and perceived expectations from others significantly influence consumers' intentions to buy green cosmetics. This outcome aligns with the studies conducted by Ahsan and Ferdinando (2023) and Hoo et al. (2024). The subjective norm was found to have a statistically significant impact on the intention to purchase organic cosmetics (Ahsan & Ferdinando, 2023). In addition, the subjective norm has a substantial association with purchasing intention towards green cosmetics products in Malaysia (Hoo et al., 2024). The result of this study ($\beta = 0.341$) demonstrates a moderate effect size, meaning that subjective norms significantly contribute to the formation of green cosmetics purchase intention among generation Z in Ho Chi Minh City.

The study also indicates a substantial positive correlation between the intention to acquire green cosmetics (GI) and the actual purchase behavior of green cosmetics (GB), with a $\beta = 0.449$. The discovery corresponds with previous research that underscores the robust connection between purchasing intentions and behavior. Green purchase intention is a significant predictor of green purchase behavior, demonstrating that a consumer's purchase intention directly and favorably influences their purchasing behavior (Naz et al., 2020). Green purchase intention positively influences green purchase behavior, as intention promotes purchasing habits (Kumar & Pandey, 2023).

5.2 Social media effect to Altruistic Motivation, Egoistic Motivation and Subjective Norms

This study's findings indicate that social media strongly affects both altruistic and egoistic motivations among generation Z consumers in Ho Chi Minh City, hence influencing their propensity to purchase green cosmetics. The path analysis indicates that social media exerts a moderate effect on altruistic motivation ($\beta = 0.284$), although its influence on egoistic motivation is marginally stronger ($\beta = 0.335$). These findings underscore the dual function of social media in influencing motivation, encompassing both altruistic and egocentric tendencies, regarding sustainable consumption behavior.

The conclusion is corroborated by the studies of Alam et al. (2023) and Pop et al. (2020). Social networks can disseminate altruistic information and enhance awareness of environmental issues, encouraging individuals to adopt eco-friendly behaviors, hence increasing purchase intentions (Alam et al., 2023). In the realm of green cosmetics, social media can impact customers' environmental awareness by promoting the acquisition of eco-friendly cosmetics (Pop et al., 2020).

On the other hand, the stronger influence of social media on egoistic motivation ($\beta = 0.335$) suggests that social media's persuasive power also extends to self-focused desires, such as enhancing personal image or status. The result is similar to the past study (Kumar & Pandey, 2023).

Customer's egoistic motivations are positively impacted by social media, which implies that social media may have an impact on consumers' health concerns regarding environmentally friendly cosmetics and assist them in choosing health-promoting products (Alam et al., 2023).

The correlation between social media and subjective norms, evidenced by the notable positive path coefficient ($\beta = 0.243$), highlights the considerable impact that social media has on individuals' perceived social expectations. The discovery corresponds with prior studies that have recorded the impact of social media platforms on subjective norms. Individuals persuaded by social media marketing are readily swayed by normative standards within sustainable consumption groups (Sun & Wang, 2019). Additionally, celebrities could be engaged to lead campaigns that emphasize the detrimental effects of certain daily behaviors and outline the dos and don'ts that foster environmental awareness among female and young consumers on social media (Sun & Wang, 2019). Social media significantly influences subjective norms about green products (Kumar & Pandey, 2023). The research identified a positive correlation ($\beta = 0.243$) attributed to the unique characteristics of social media, including immediate feedback, social validation mechanisms (e.g., likes, shares, and comments), and the extensive reach of digital influencers. These elements create a digital ecosystem where individuals are perpetually subjected to normative expectations, hence augmenting subjective norms.

5.3 Electronic Word-Of-Mouth (EWOM) effects to Green Cosmetics Purchase Behavior

Electronic word-of-mouth (EWOM) has a substantial positive correlation with green cosmetics purchasing behavior ($\beta = 0.254$). The finding is consistent with research of (Kumar & Pandey, 2023) that underscores the pivotal role of EWOM in shaping sustainable consumer behavior. According to (Kumar & Pandey, 2023), one important predictor of green buying behavior was found to be EWOM.

6. CONCLUSION

Social media significantly influences the actions of generation Z. social media platforms function as essential tools for propagating environmental awareness and advocating for sustainable consumption through their capacity to connect, inform, and influence. In addition to social media, personal incentives significantly influence green purchase decisions. Consumer intentions are shaped by both egoistic (health considerations) and altruistic (environmental concerns) motivations. Moreover, subjective norms, defined as the perceived social pressures to engage in ecologically sustainable actions, further bolster these behaviors. This study effectively underscores the influence of social media on altruistic and egoistic motivations, together with subjective norms, which collectively determine the

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buying intentions of generation Z in Ho Chi Minh City. Furthermore, electronic word-of-mouth (EWOM) has become a significant influence in customer decision-making. When a product corresponds with promotion-oriented objectives, buyers demonstrate a positivity bias, perceiving favorable reviews as more compelling. In contrast, when a product is associated with prevention-oriented objectives, consumers exhibit a negative bias, regarding negative reviews as more impactful. This highlights the necessity of comprehending consumer motivations and regulatory focus in developing effective marketing strategies and managing product evaluations.

Purchase behavior for green cosmetics was impacted both directly and indirectly by independent and mediating factors. The most important predictor of green cosmetics purchase behavior is egoistic motivation, which is also the main driver of green cosmetics buying intention. One significant component is social media, which has a direct impact on motivations and subjective norms while also indirectly influencing behavior through GI. Additionally, GB is significantly impacted directly by EWOM. Lastly, the best indicator of green cosmetics purchase behavior is green cosmetics purchase intention.

Social media is an important tool for raising awareness, increasing eco-consciousness, and boosting purchase intentions by authentic storytelling and balanced message that appeals to both altruistic (environmental) and egoistic (health) motivations. Businesses can boost their credibility by promoting Electronic Word-Of-Mouth, working with influencers, and supporting user-generated content. Emphasizing transparency, sustainability, and product performance is critical, as is customizing marketing to local cultural norms. Furthermore, promoting community engagement through interactive campaigns and adhering to societal norms boost brand loyalty and advocacy. By combining these techniques, green cosmetics companies can effectively connect with Generation Z while also contributing to sustainable consumer behavior.

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